

STUDIES IN THE COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS. PART XVI.
FURTHER INVESTIGATION OF THE "ZONAL EFFECT" AND
THE ANOMALOUS VARIATIONS OF THE VISCOSITY,
TRANSPARENCY AND REFRACTIVITY DURING
THE COAGULATIONS OF COLLOID ANTIMONY
SULPHIDE BY AQUEOUS MERCURY
CHLORIDE.

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In Part XIV of this series (Joshi and Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 439) it was reported that coagulations of colloid arsenious sulphide by aqueous *mercury chloride* showed a markedly unusual feature, *viz.*, that the viscosity, the transparency and opacity (measured independently from determinations of transparency) *remained almost constant during the coagulation time*. The familiar variations due to coagulation in these properties under the same conditions of experiment were observed when other electrolytes in appropriate amounts were used as coagulants, and also when but small amounts of any one of them were mixed with mercury chloride. In view of the definitely unusual character of these findings, it was considered desirable to examine this effect with a different system *viz.*, antimony sulphide sol. Furthermore, studies of the numerous coagulations of colloid manganese dioxide due both to electrolytes and oppositely charged sols (Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, 1936, 18, 309; Joshi and Jaya Rao, *ibid.*, 1936, 18, 311; *Fettchem. Umsch.*, 1936, 43, 36; *Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 76, 145; *Current Science*, 1936, 4, 481; Joshi and Purushottam, *ibid.*, 1936, 4, 870) showed that the refractivity varied 'zonally' in the *slow* region. This 'zonal effect' was also observed in diverse coagulations of dilute oil suspensions by electrolytes (Joshi and Sarkar, *J. Bomb. Univ.*, 1935, 4, 140) including mercury chloride, studied refractometrically. Experiments were also made, therefore, with colloid antimony sulphide employing the last named method of following a coagulation, as developed in these laboratories to investigate the generality of the 'zonal effect' recorded, it would appear for the first time in the literature on coagulation kinetics, in Part XI of this series.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Colloid antimony sulphide was prepared as described earlier (Joshi and Prabhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11) and dialysed against repeated

changes of distilled water till the dialysate was free from the acid. It was stocked in a carefully cleaned Jena bottle and its colloid content determined by Kessler's method (*Pogg. Ann.* 1863, 118, 17; *cf.* also Joshi and Prabhu. *loc. cit.*). Some of the typical results for the variation of n_D , the refractive index, due to different concentrations of the mercury chloride varied in the region 0.009 to 0.002N during different coagulations, have been shown graphically in Fig. 1. It was found that under sensibly identical conditions of observation, the variation of n_D during a coagulation was not fully reproducible. Two of the results of such repeat experiments are

FIG. 1.

Variation of refractivity during coagulation.

shown by curves 1, 1a, 2, 2a, 3, 3a, and 5, 5a in Fig. 1. In the coagulation corresponding to curve 2a, the observation of n_D was discontinued at the point (40, 160) and resumed at the point (160, 215). It will be seen, however, that the principal zonal effect in the time-variation of n_D during a given coagulation is sufficiently persis-

tent and brought out by both series of the curves. The temperature of the coagulating system was maintained at $34 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The general procedure and precautions were the same as described previously (Joshi and Rao, *loc. cit.*). The variation of η , the viscosity of the same colloid in the presence of HgCl_2 was studied in the range 0.0009 to 0.0013N by Scarpa's method with modifications described previously (Joshi and Menon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 599). Only four typical curves for η -change are given in Fig. 2. Results for the change of intensity of light transmitted during the coagulation as recorded with a thermopile (*cf.* Joshi and Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*, also Joshi and Rao, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 311) are shown graphically in Fig. 3. In order to obtain confirmation of these results, transparency of the colloid was also measured by using a Duboscq colorimeter (*cf.* Joshi and Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*). The data are shown in Fig. 4. In order to prevent overlapping of the curves and especially to economise the figure space, different co-ordinate axes have been used for curves in a given series; their origin, position and the scale units have been indicated in the figure.

DISCUSSION.

The results for the variation of n_D , the refractivity during the coagulation of colloid antimony sulphide by mercury chloride as seen from curves in Fig. 1 are in complete agreement with earlier results mentioned in the introduction. Also, as found previously (Joshi and Rao, *Kolloid Z.*, *loc. cit.*; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 311) on colloid manganese dioxide and dilute oil-suspensions (Joshi and Sarkar, *loc. cit.*) coagulated by different coagulants, comparison of curves 2, 2a, 3, 3a with 1, 1a, 4, 5 and 5a shows that *maximum zonal effect is observed only with moderate concentrations of the coagulant. For much larger and much smaller values of the last quantity, the net change in n_D as also the number of zones tends to diminish.* In this connection it is interesting to point out that in numerous measurements of different colloids, η , the viscosity, varied discontinuously or through a number of breaks in the *slow* region (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329; Joshi and Menon, *loc. cit.*; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 133; Joshi and Iyengar, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 555, 573; Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 797; *Proc. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1935, 8, 41; *J. chim. phys.*, 1935, 32, 455; Joshi and Sarkar, *loc. cit.*). The results now obtained confirm this. It is seen, for example, from Fig. 2 that while η rises pronouncedly in coagulations corresponding to curves 1, 2 and 3 in Fig. 2, the definite effect of any further diminishing the coagulant concentration is seen in the marked increase in the number of breaks or disconti-

nities as seen in curve 4, Fig. 2. The net increase in η due to coagulation is also much less in the latter than in *rapid* coagulations. It is seen therefore, that the influence of mercury chloride on n_D and η in the case of

FIG. 2.

colloid antimony sulphide is analogous to that of other electrolytic coagulants in respect of the general finding in these laboratories, *viz.*, the *zonal character of a slow coagulation*. It must also be recorded at this stage that the previous result that mercuric chloride, whilst producing coagulation of colloid arsenious sulphide over the whole concentration range investigated definitely failed to produce a net rise of viscosity in by far the majority of cases studied (*cf.* Part XIV), does not find analogy with the colloid studied now.

A comparison of the curves in Figs. 3 and 4 for the variation of the transparency determined by thermopile and colorimeter respectively with corresponding curves for coagulations of colloid arsenious sulphide in the

presence of mercuric chloride reported earlier (Part XIV, *loc. cit.*), reveals that the above property varies in a way which depends upon the concentration of the coagulant. At low values of the last quantity, the transparency diminishes (Fig. 3) and the capacity increases (Fig. 4) during just the initial stage of coagulation; they remain almost constant subsequently. During this time the process of coagulation had progressed producing perceptible flocculation; although the corresponding transparency and opacity (Figs. 3 and 4) had not changed in the familiar manner. The marked increase in transparency subsequent to its reaching a minimum in curve 6 in Fig. 3 corresponding to the maximum concentration of the coagulant employed was due to the settling of the coagulum produced by an appreciable flocculation during the latter stages. It is seen, therefore, that the anomalous behaviour of mercury chloride in failing to produce rise in opacity (and its reverse) in flocculations of colloid arsenious sulphide (*cf.* part XIV) is also observed in the case of the present sol as long as the concentration of the coagulant is low. This finding has a marked interest in relation to the occurrence of 'zones' brought out especially by the

refractivity measurements ; which suggest that *in the slow region* corresponding to the horizontal sections in the n_D -time curves (Fig. 1), either (i) the refractivity is invariant (or, at any rate has a markedly altered time-rate) despite the occurrence of coagulation, or (ii) that the coagulation comes to a standstill for a period, re-starts, to be followed by another phase of partial or almost complete inactivity and so on, periodically, till flocculation changes into the precipitation of the coagulum.

FIG. 4.

S U M M A R Y.

1. The coagulation of colloid antimony sulphide has been followed in the *slow region* by observations of change of refractivity, viscosity, transparency and capacity in the presence of aqueous mercuric chloride. 2. Viscosity and especially refractivity changes show discontinuities or zones of coagulation, which become most conspicuous in the *medium slow region*. 3. Transparency (and the separately measured opacity) remains almost stationary except during initial stages, with small concentrations of the coagulant, which is partly similar to earlier results (Part XIV, in this series) on colloid arsenious sulphide with the same coagulant, when viscosity, transparency and opacity were found to be invariant over the whole range of the HgCl₂ concentrations examined.